

ARGOS

Conceptual Design Study

Designing a Next-Generation Radio Facility for Multi-Messenger Astronomy

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List of Abbreviations

ARGOS	Astronomy for Radio Observatory and Signal Observation System
CDS	Conceptual Design Study
SE	Systems Engineering
TCS	Telescope Control System
PDR	Preliminary Design Review
CDR	Critical Design Review
SEMP	Systems Engineering Management Plan
ADC	Analog to Digital Converter
RFSoc	Radio Frequency System on Chip
RFI	Radio Frequency Interference
FRB	Fast Radio Burst
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
SEP	Systems Engineering Plan
EU	European Union
HVAC	Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning
COTS	Commercial Off-The-Shelf
CD	Conceptual Design
PMP	Project Management Plan
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
SUC	Science Use Cases
TLR	Technology Readiness Level
RF	Radio Frequency
WP	Work Package
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
FMEA	Failure Modes and Effects Analysis
FTA	Fault Tree Analysis
FFBD	Functional flow block diagrams
LNA	Low-Noise Amplifier
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Array
AI	Artificial Intelligence

1. Introduction

Purpose of the document

The purpose of the Systems Engineering Management Plan (SEMP) is to provide a structured, high-level technical planning of the engineering activities of the ARGOS project (including the ARGOS-CDS [1]) in order to communicate to the team itself, the managers, the EU officers, and relevant stakeholders the technical effort that will be performed by the assigned technical team.

Scope of the document

This SEMP describes the approach, activities, products, processes, tools and controls that will be developed and used during the life cycle of the project. This document also coordinates the engineering effort in a coherent and efficient manner in order to ensure the successful deployment and commissioning of the ARGOS telescope. Apart from the technical aspects, the SEMP describes, and provides templates for the documentation that should be produced for the review at the end of each major milestone of the project. The present document is tightly coupled with the Project Management Plan (PMP) that has been produced in the context of the ARGOS Conceptual Design Study project, funded by the EU under G.A. 101094354 [2].

Content of the document

The document is organized as follows: In Section 2, *References*, the relevant documents to this SEMP are provided. In Section 3, ARGOS Overview, a short description of Systems Engineering (SE) and its significance to ARGOS is provided, along with an overview of the project and its mission and objectives. In Section 4, Systems Engineering Plan, the organizational structure as well as the distribution of competences within the ARGOS project are described. In Section 5, System Engineering Phases and Process, *the ARGOS* engineering phases are presented, while in Section 6, Control, all relevant reviews and audits, risk management and requirements traceability functionalities are described in order to ensure an unburdened operation of the final product. In Section 7, Retirement, all necessary action for the retirement and the preservation of the project's assets is described. Finally, in Section 8, Documentation and Additional Activities, general guidelines for the necessary documents to be produced are provided, relevant templates and examples. Other activities, for instance dissemination actions, are herein described as well. Reporting and deliverable templates are provided in Appendix A. Effort has been made for the SEMP to be in conformance with the ISO/IEC/IEEE 24748-4 standard [3].

This SEMP is a living document and it will be regularly updated as needed throughout the project's life cycle.

2. References

Applicable documents [1-2, 6, 8-12]

In the event of conflict between the contents of the following documents and this document, the following documents shall take precedence.

Reference documents [3-5, 7, 13-6]

These additional documents are referenced in the text. In the event of conflict between the contents of the following documents and this document, this document shall take precedence.

- [1] GRANT AGREEMENT Project 101094354- ARGOS -CDS, EUROPEAN RESEARCH EXECUTIVE AGENCY (REA).
- [2] J. Antoniadis, "ARGOS-CDS D1.4: Project Management Plan".
- [3] ISO/IEC/IEEE 24748 Systems and software engineering — Life cycle management Part 4: Systems engineering planning, 2016.
- [4] INCOSE Systems Engineering Handbook A Guide for System Life Cycle Processes and Activities., John Wiley & Sons, 2015.
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- [13] ISO/IEC/IEEE 16326 Systems and software engineering — Life cycle processes — Project management, 2019.
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- [15] W. Chen, E. Barr, N. Esser and Y. Men, "ARGOS-CDS D6.1: Backend simulations and prototyping report".
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3. ARGOS Overview

Systems Engineering (SE) can be defined as [4]: “a transdisciplinary and integrative approach to enable the successful realization, use, and retirement of engineered systems, using systems principles and concepts, and scientific, technological, and management methods.” The intention of building a European radio telescope for continuous wide-field monitoring of the sky, while publicly distributing science-ready data and alerts in real time, demands an SE approach so as to maximize the probability of success. The SE approach described in the rest of the document is tailored to the needs of the ARGOS project such that best collaboration and responsibility is established among all involved parties.

High-level description

ARGOS is a concept of technology readiness level 2 out of 9 (TLR 2) for a leading-edge, low-cost, sustainable “small-D, big-N” European radio interferometer. A high-level graphical representation of the ARGOS infrastructure is depicted in Figure 1. The design that is currently under development assumes that the array consists of 1200 6-m parabolic antennas, deployed over a 4x4 km area.

The 6-m parabolic antennas are placed on motorized mounts and host the radio-frequency (RF) frontend which involves the dual-polarization feeder, low-noise amplifiers (LNAs), RF filters and associated performance and health monitoring equipment, ensuring efficient signal capture. The backend subsystem is comprised of digitizers, FPGAs, polyphase filterbanks & channelizers, high speed fiber optics network interfaces and switches, graphical processing unit (GPU) and storage nodes, a Faraday container, and a maser-based observatory clock for precise timekeeping . Moreover, solar panels and batteries, assisted by proper power management can provide a backup power source and lower the running costs of the facility.

The software subsystems feature a comprehensive suite including the Telescope Control System (TCS), various user interfaces, the system health management unit, the beamformer/correlator, the calibration pipelines for phasing the array, as well as various science processing pipelines, and an archiving and alerts unit.

This integrated system aims to enable advanced capabilities in radio astronomy, including real-time data processing, accurate source localization, and effective big data storage and analysis. Overall, the project is designed to push the boundaries of current astronomical research through the deployment of state-of-the-art and novel technologies in radio astronomy and computational astrophysics.

Schematic description

In Figure 1, a high-level overview of ARGOS is shown. ARGOS consists of a large number of antennas (1200), equipped with 6-meter diameter parabolic dishes, mounted on motorized elevation – azimuth turnheads. Each antenna carries an RF frontend with a 3D-printed horn dual-polarity feeder, and a custom analog stage with filters and LNAs which is tuned in the 1 – 3 GHz frequency range. The RF Backend is directly connected to the frontend for minimum losses and incorporates 4 high sampling rate ADCs directly interfaced to an FPGA within an RFSoc block. The FPGA is providing the channelization of the digitized spectrum and the data are transferred over a 100 GbE optical network interface to the facility that hosts the active network and computing infrastructure. The 100 GbE network switches follow the folded Clos topology in order to provide the channelized data via

multicast to multiple computing nodes simultaneously. The data are processed by the GPUs and the CPUs of the nodes that comprise the server cluster. The server cluster follows the hyperconverged paradigm by each server hosting both the computing and the storage units, interconnected by the same multi-100 GbE network that serves the antennas. The archiving and alerting subsystem stores and provides the results to the community via high-speed Internet connectivity.

Figure 1: High-level overview of ARGOS

In Figure 2, a schematic diagram of the ARGOS subsystems is depicted. The interaction between the subsystems is denoted with colored arrows; red & orange show control & signaling, and green show the actual flow of captured and processed data. There are four major high-level sub-systems (frontend, backend, science processing, archiving & alerting), telescope control system (TCS) and its user interface, and the clock that provides highly accurate frequency and time reference. Moreover, the archiving and alerting subsystem provides the results to the rest of the world.

Figure 2: ARGOS sub-systems interaction

Goals and ambition

ARGOS's ambition is to open the dynamic radio sky for exploration, searching for multi-messenger signals with high speed and sensitivity, while delivering science-ready datasets to the public.

ARGOS will be able to simultaneously address 6 fundamental science goals:

1. Fast Radio Burst and the Nature of Dark Matter, Dark Energy and Primordial Magnetism
2. The Transient and Violent Universe
3. Gravitational Wave Counterparts
4. nHz Gravitational Waves and the Early Universe
5. Fundamental Physics Using Pulsars
6. Technology Pathfinding and Exploitation

ARGOS challenges

Throughout the lifecycle of the project, it is essential to address several engineering challenges. These challenges, encompassing scalability, durability, technological readiness, and future-proofing, require a structured and proactive approach.

Scalability and Cost Control

- **Reduction of Unit Cost:** Due to the large number of dishes, achieving cost efficiency for each dish without compromising performance is critical. It will be necessary to develop streamlined designs utilizing modular, low-cost materials and automated assembly processes, enabling cost-effective mass production.

- **Enhanced Component Durability:** To ensure continuous operation without frequent maintenance or replacements, components should be designed for durability, utilizing weather-resistant materials and incorporating remote diagnostic capabilities for predictive maintenance.
- **Industrial Partnerships for Mass Manufacturing:** Strategic partnerships with industrial manufacturers will be crucial for producing large quantities of dishes, feeds, turn heads, and samplers.
- **Optimized Construction Timeline:** To address potential bottlenecks the construction plan may require concurrent assembly methods. Consideration should be given to dividing construction tasks across multiple teams or regions to enable a more distributed, efficient build process.

Adapting to the Rapid Evolution of Key Technologies

- **Flexible Procurement for Processing Power, Storage, and Networking:** To leverage advancements in GPU processing, storage, and networking technologies, the SEMP should establish a flexible procurement strategy. This will allow for the acquisition of the most efficient hardware available at the time of purchase. Regular technology reviews during the design phase are recommended to align specifications with the latest available advancements.
- **Strategic Software-Defined Telescope Approach:** As ARGOS is, to a large extent, software-defined, a roadmap for regular software updates aligned with hardware capabilities is essential. This will address real-time data processing challenges, such as visibility data handling and RFI flagging, ensuring adaptability to evolving data science capabilities.
- **Optimization of Scientific Output:** The SEMP should specify adaptable configurations for software, enabling ARGOS to leverage future advancements in hardware. This will allow dynamic adjustments to scientific outputs, such as maximum dispersion measure for FRB searches or spectroscopy capabilities, based on available computing power and storage capacity.
- **Scalable Data Handling Architecture:** A scalable data architecture is critical to adapt to increasing data volumes and complexity. Potential solutions may include cloud-based storage or modular storage arrays, which can be expanded in alignment with ARGOS's growth.

Each of these areas should be accompanied by clearly defined performance metrics and regular review intervals within the SEMP. This approach will ensure that ARGOS meets its initial scientific objectives and remains adaptable as it scales over time.

4. Systems Engineering Plan

The Systems Engineering Plan (SEP) outlines the strategic framework and methodology for preparing, organizing and managing the engineering efforts required to develop and deploy ARGOS.

This section provides a comprehensive roadmap that details:

- the project objectives,
- working groups,
- budget allocation,
- timelines and milestones,
- risk management,
- quality assurance processes.

By establishing clear goals and responsibilities, a detailed work breakdown structure (WBS), an essential part of the SEP, ensures that the system as a whole with all comprising components and subsystems is cohesively integrated and aligned with the project's vision.

Objective

ARGOS aims to design, develop, and deploy a radio interferometer comprising approximately 1200 antennas (big N) of 6-meter diameter (small D) each, for advanced astronomical observations. The objective of the SEP is to manage the engineering aspects of the project throughout its entire lifecycle. This includes ensuring that the project progresses seamlessly through the design phase, where concepts are developed and requirements are translated into technical specifications; the deployment phase, which involves the integration, testing, and commissioning of the system in its operational environment; the operations phase, where the system is monitored, maintained, and optimized to deliver its intended functionality and meet stakeholder expectations; and finally, the retirement phase, which addresses the safe and efficient decommissioning of the system, including disposal, archiving of data, and lessons learned. The SEP ensures that each phase is executed effectively, with clear objectives, documented processes, risk mitigation strategies, and stakeholder alignment, ultimately delivering a system that meets its performance, cost, and schedule requirements while adhering to quality standards.

Working groups

The successful execution of the project will rely on a diverse and specialized workforce, organized into distinct working groups, each contributing their unique expertise to different aspects of the project. The personnel involved will primarily belong to one of the following key working groups:

Management: The management working group will guide the project through its various phases, ensuring that timelines are adhered to and milestones are achieved. Their role is crucial in coordinating efforts across different teams and managing resources efficiently. They will also ensure to maintain communication with stakeholders and ensure alignment among all working groups. The lead role of the management working group is the **Project Manager**, thus they should have strong leadership qualities, extensive project management experience, excellent communication skills, and expertise in resource management.

Science: This group will focus on further developing and enhancing the scientific goals of the facility, defining research objectives, ensuring the system's design aligns with scientific requirements, and conducting data analysis once the system is operational. The team will comprise of experts in astronomy, cosmology and astrophysics, as well as specialists in artificial intelligence (AI), big data, and data analytics, ensuring a multidisciplinary approach to achieving the project's scientific aims. This working group will be led by the **Science Director**, responsible for steering the scientific vision of the project, prioritizing research objectives, and ensuring that the project's scientific goals are achieved.

Systems Engineering: Systems engineers, led by the **Systems Engineering Manager**, will play a pivotal role in designing and integrating the various subsystems of the interferometer, ensuring seamless interoperability and optimal performance. They are further organized into three subgroups:

Frontend Engineers: RF engineers are indispensable for the design, integration and development of the RF components, which include the antennas, feeders, filters, and amplifiers. Their expertise will ensure that the interferometer can capture and process signals with high precision. This subgroup is led by the **RF Lead Engineer**.

Backend Engineers: Complementing the frontend team, backend engineers will design, integrate, and develop the digitization units, initial signal processing units, data processing pipelines, signal correlation systems, and storage solutions needed to process and manage the vast amounts of data generated by the interferometer. The backend team is led by the **Backend Lead Engineer**.

Software Engineers: Charged with designing and customizing the necessary software infrastructure for data processing, system control, and user interfaces, this team will ensure seamless integration of software components with the system's hardware. They will supervise the software developers who will be tasked with creating the custom software necessary for data acquisition, processing, analysis, storage, and retrieval. This software will be the backbone of the system, transforming raw data into actionable insights. This subgroup is led by the **Software Lead Engineer**.

Quality assurance: The Quality Assurance (QA) group will play a critical role in ensuring that all aspects of the project meet the agreed upon standards of performance, reliability, and that the end product complies with technical requirements. This team will be responsible for establishing and enforcing quality control processes, conducting regular inspections, and verifying that both hardware and software components conform to the required operational standards. Comprised of specialists in system validation, testing, and regulatory compliance, the QA team will work closely with engineers and technical staff to identify potential issues early in the development process and ensure that any defects are corrected before deployment. Their ongoing oversight will ensure that the telescope operates as expected, with minimal risk of performance degradation or failure. The team will be overseen by the **QA manager**.

Assembly/Integration/Verification: The Assembly/Integration/Verification (AIV) group will be responsible for the physical installation, integration, and verification of the system components. The AIV team, led by the **AIV manager**, will oversee all assembly processes, ensuring that each component is accurately installed and aligned according to technical specifications. They will manage on-site logistics, coordinating the delivery and handling of equipment and materials to support a smooth assembly process. The group is also tasked with performing verification procedures to confirm system functionality and compliance with design requirements before transitioning to operations.

Operations: The **Operations Manager** and their group will oversee the day-to-day functioning of the system after installation. Their responsibilities include monitoring and maintaining all operational components to ensure ongoing reliability and performance. This team will handle routine maintenance, diagnose and resolve technical issues and implement operational adjustments. Additionally, they will manage system updates, maintain records of operational activities, and provide support for continuous system improvements and troubleshooting throughout the lifecycle of the project.

Administration: Supporting the operational aspects of the project, the administrative team will handle logistics, documentation, procurement, and other essential administrative tasks to ensure smooth day-to-day operations. The administration working group will be coordinated by the **Administrative Coordinator**, who will handle all administrative aspects of the project.

Resource and budget allocation

In the context of systems engineering, resource and budget allocation involves analyzing the project's needs, estimating the required resources for each work package or task (derived from the Work Breakdown Structure (WBS)), and allocating the appropriate funds and assets to ensure smooth operation. This requires balancing limited resources against project objectives while continuously monitoring and adjusting allocations to manage risks and changes as the project progresses.

The successful execution of the ARGOS project necessitates a thorough approach to resource and budget allocation, ensuring that all components and subsystems, comprising the project, are adequately funded.

The list below outlines the essential hardware equipment required for the project's construction, along with some essential works and constructions:

- Passive equipment:
 - Cables – Single Mode Fiber Optic, Copper Cat.6 UTP/SFTP, Electrical, Conduits, accessories
 - Antennas – 6m parabolic dishes, motorized mounts, feeders, accessories
 - Energy – Solar panels, batteries, safety devices, electrical panels
- Active equipment:
 - Clocks – Hydrogen Maser
 - Digitizers – RFSoc based ADCs + FPGAs
 - Networking – 100/200/400/800 GbE Switches, optical QSFP28/56/-DD modules, DACs
 - Servers – GPU Processing, Archiving and distribution
 - Electrical grid – UPSs, generators, inverters
- Works / Constructions:
 - Cables – Conduit and pillar installations, terminations, splicing
 - Antennas – Concrete foundations
 - Clocks – Anechoic chamber construction (space, energy, cooling, RFI, and vibration requirements fulfilment)
 - Networking – Racks hosting (space, energy, and cooling requirements fulfilment) and installation
 - Servers – Racks hosting (space, energy, and cooling requirements fulfilment) and installation
 - Other facilities – Personnel hosting, lighting, warning/safety/surveillance/emergency systems, fencing, paths/roads, drainage systems

Custom software development represents another major budget item. This involves developing data processing algorithms, user interfaces, and control systems tailored to the specific needs of the ARGOS project. Extensive testing and calibration are critical to ensure the system's accuracy and reliability. Therefore, a portion of the budget must be allocated to this aspect to validate the system's performance.

Long-term maintenance and potential upgrades are also key considerations. Allocating funds for routine maintenance and unforeseen repairs will ensure the system's longevity and consistent performance.

Additionally, investing in training and development for personnel is crucial. Workshops and continuous education programs will equip the team with the necessary skills to operate and maintain the system effectively.

Finally, it is prudent to include a contingency fund within the budget. This reserve will provide a financial buffer to address any unexpected costs that may arise, ensuring the project's stability and success.

Timelines and Milestones:

ARGOS may be built in an iterative fashion, depending on the funding or equipment availability. The modularity and distributed scheme of its infrastructure enables the construction in multiple steps, enlarging the system by each iteration, up to its full scale.

Project Total Timeline: # TBE months

Initial Planning: # TBE months

Design Phase: # TBE months

Procurement and Fabrication: # TBE months

Installation and Integration: # TBE months

Testing and Validation: # TBE months

Deployment and Commissioning: # TBE months

Key Milestones:

1. Completion of design blueprints
 - Full scale deployment blueprints
 - Full scale electrical grid
 - Full scale network grid
 - All buildings and constructions required
2. Installation site preparation – First minimum viable setup
 - antenna foundations
 - buildings & facilities
 - roads / paths
 - conduits
 - electrical grid
 - HVAC
3. First partial antenna array completion
 - Delivery of equipment – First batch
 - Antennas, feeders, and accessories
 - electronic components
 - custom components
 - Servers and networking equipment
 - other COTS equipment
 - Passive and active infrastructure installations – First batch
 - Passive infrastructure installation
 - First batch of antennas installation (complete with feeders and active components)
 - Active network components installation
 - Server cluster installation
4. First system integration test and initial science verification
 - Electrical grid testing
 - HVAC testing
 - Individual components testing and performance verification
 - Integration and interoperability tests of all components
 - Science requirements verification/validation

5. Intermediate antenna array expansions, system integration tests, and science verifications
6. Full antenna array completion
7. Completion of system integration tests and science verification

Risk Management

Effective risk management is crucial for ensuring the success of ARGOS (and ARGOS-CDS). The Risk Management Plan involves identifying potential risks, developing strategies to mitigate them, and continuously monitoring these risks throughout the project's lifecycle. Potential risks are categorized as technical, schedule, or budget risks. Each category has first to be identified and then mitigation actions should take place. So, in that order:

Risk Identification

Technical Risks: These include the potential for failure or under-performance of critical components, integration issues between subsystems, or unforeseen technical challenges in achieving the system's performance requirements (e.g., sensitivity, resolution).

Schedule Risks: Delays in component delivery, unexpected technical challenges during system integration, or staffing shortages could impact the project's timeline.

Budget Risks: Cost overruns may occur due to unforeseen technical issues, changes in project scope, or the need for additional resources or contingency measures.

Risk Mitigation Strategies

Redundant Systems for Critical Components: To reduce the risk of single points of failure, redundant systems will be incorporated for critical components. This ensures system reliability and minimizes downtime in case of component failures.

Contingency Budget for Unforeseen Expenses: A contingency budget will be allocated to account for unexpected costs, such as the need for additional resources, equipment failures, or rework due to technical issues. This financial buffer will prevent budget constraints from delaying the project.

Regular Progress Reviews and Adaptive Scheduling: Progress will be monitored closely through regular reviews, allowing for early detection of issues and the adjustment of timelines when necessary. An adaptive scheduling approach will enable the project to remain flexible, accommodating any unforeseen challenges without significantly impacting overall project delivery.

In more detail, the risks that may occur in ARGOS can be listed with the aforementioned categorization and be divided in to seven categories as follows:

- Budget underestimation (budget risk)
Budget planning may be derailed, especially when events with global impact occur, e.g. pandemics, wars, factories (of specialized hardware) destruction, etc.
- Time underestimation (schedule risk)
Smaller or larger time delays may always occur, but in the case where there is a dependency between the tasks, a cascaded increase in delay will occur
- Resources underestimation (schedule risk)
Depending on the planned tasks effort, unprovisioned difficulties/complexities or disability to attract specialized personnel may occur

- Overheads (budget and schedule risk)
Non-planned overheads, both in cost and time may occur due to taxation changes and bureaucratic implications.
- Specifications mismatch (technical risk)
Specifications may not always be met due to multiple reasons, such as, products becoming obsolete, products cannot be purchased due to abrupt increase in cost, vendor infidelity, lack of alternatives
- Deployment Location (technical risk)
The deployment location has to fulfill many specifications and a significant one is the minimum RFI, which is not easy to discover and use, at least in easily accessible places.
- Interoperability issues (technical risk)
In complex systems there is always the possibility of underperforming as a whole, although each separate component performs as expected, due to non-ideal interoperability issues

The respective mitigation strategies are:

- Budget underestimation
Calculate an initial small overhead and have a backup plan with lower cost components or a downsized but good performing system.
- Time underestimation
Some short-time delays should be estimated and included in the planning, based on the nature of the task and the most probable time extensions that may be required.
- Resources underestimation
This may be provisioned with some extra time buffers and in advance personnel recruitment probing.
- Overheads
Extra time and budget should be provisioned as described in the first two strategies.
- Specifications
Design and select equipment with as many alternatives as possible, have at least a second device, model, vendor, constructor, etc. considered as a backup plan.
- Deployment Location
The frontend and backend should be optimized or easily customized for use in high RFI environments.
- Interoperability issues
Components should be tested in pairs in order to detect mismatches and correct them in early stages. Also, the integration of extra components or alternative ones in order to solve the issues should always be considered.

Further information on risk management of ARGOS can be found in [2].

Risk management and risk mitigation strategies in ARGOS-CDS

- Pathfinder downsizing:
 - The initial plan was to build an array of 16 antennas and their respective server cluster to support them. The increase in the cost of components (and for some it was extreme, i.e. maser clock) led to the downsizing of the array and the supporting server cluster, in order to have a minimum viable system. (budget risk mitigation)
- Specifications mismatch:
 - The selected parabolic dish specifications were updated after the shipment of the dish by the vendor (the weight doubled). The motorized mount can support the updated specification. Overprovisioning was essential. (technical risk mitigation)

- Pathfinder site location:
 - The initial estimation of hosting the pathfinder at the Skinakas observatory was rejected due to increased RFI. A specific part of the FORTH campus was selected as it has the advantage of all the existing facilities and a manageable RFI. Within that specific part of the campus, two alternative positions were chosen and only one can be used. (technical risk mitigation)
- Equipment acquisition delays:
 - Specialized equipment is not easy to acquire, especially when the budget is limited and the bureaucratic procedures are slow. The market survey and vendors communication started early in order to have the equipment on time. (schedule risk mitigation)
- Personnel hiring delays:
 - Specialized personnel are not easy to attract, especially in the public sector when private sector offers better pay grades. Work is performed from existing personnel in order not to accumulate very long delays. (schedule risk mitigation)

Integration of SEP with Other Project Plans

The SEP must be seamlessly integrated with other critical project plans to ensure the smooth execution and successful completion of ARGOS (-CDS). This integration ensures that technical, managerial, and operational aspects are fully aligned across all domains of the project. We now briefly discuss how this integration with the PMP [2], the Quality Assurance Plan (QAP) and the Configuration Management Plan (CMP) should take place.

Project Management Plan

The SEP will be fully aligned with the PMP [2] to ensure that the technical processes and risk management strategies support the overall project management objectives. This integration enables the systems engineering team to work in synchronization with project schedules, resource allocation, and key milestones. Risk management strategies defined within the SEP will be coordinated with the PMP to ensure that any emerging risks or changes in scope are addressed in real-time, enabling adaptive project control and maintaining alignment with project goals.

Quality Assurance Plan

The QAP outlines the quality objectives and standards that the project must meet throughout its lifecycle. The SEP will integrate with the QAP to ensure that quality assurance processes are embedded into every phase of the engineering lifecycle. By aligning technical requirements, verification, and validation processes with the QAP, the SEP ensures that risks related to system performance and quality are identified early, allowing for timely intervention and adjustments. Continuous feedback loops between the systems engineering team and the quality assurance team will maintain high standards in design, testing, and system integration.

Configuration Management Plan

The CMP is essential for managing changes to the system design, ensuring that modifications are systematically tracked, documented, and evaluated. The SEP will work in close coordination with the CMP to ensure that any changes made during the design and development phases are fully documented, evaluated for risk, and communicated across all relevant teams. By integrating

configuration control with risk management, the SEP ensures that design changes do not introduce unforeseen risks, maintaining the integrity and performance of the system while preventing project delays due to poorly managed modifications.

Work Breakdown Structure (WBS)

The WBS outlines the key areas of work necessary for successful project execution as it divides the project into manageable components, ensuring clear responsibilities, coordination, and alignment between scientific, technical, and operational tasks. The ARGOS key tasks framework is summarized as follows:

1. **Project and Consortium Management:** This area focuses on the overall management and coordination of the project, ensuring that all teams and consortium members are aligned, project milestones are met, and communication channels remain open. It includes managing budgets, schedules, risk management, and project documentation.
2. **Scientific Objectives (Astrophysics and Cosmology):** This section defines the scientific goals of the project, including the research focus areas in radio astronomy, cosmology, and other relevant scientific fields. It ensures that the system's design and data collection capabilities align with the scientific requirements.
3. **Systems Engineering and Design Management:** This component is responsible for the overall system architecture and ensuring that all technical subsystems, such as front-end, back-end, and signal processing units, are integrated effectively. It includes overseeing the system design process, technical coordination, and maintaining performance standards.
4. **Site Selection and Infrastructure Development:** This phase involves selecting the optimal site for the installation of the radio interferometer. It includes environmental analysis, site characterization, and the development of the necessary infrastructure, such as power supply, communication lines, and facility layout.
5. **Front-end Subsystem Development:** This area covers the design, development, and testing of the front-end hardware, such as antennas and receivers, which capture the signals from space. It ensures that the system's sensitivity, noise levels, and signal quality meet project requirements.
6. **Back-end Subsystem Development:** This part of the project focuses on the components responsible for data handling, including signal processing, correlation, and initial data storage. It ensures that the data captured by the front-end is processed efficiently and accurately.
7. **Data Processing and Analysis:** This stage involves developing real-time data processing capabilities, including signal correlation and advanced data analytics. It also includes integrating artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning models to assist with data interpretation and scientific analysis.
8. **Data Archiving and Event Alert System:** This part focuses on long-term data storage and management, ensuring that the data collected can be easily retrieved and analyzed in the future. It also involves developing an alert system to notify the scientific team when significant events or discoveries are detected in the data.
9. **Outreach, Communication, and Data Dissemination:** This area handles public communication, stakeholder engagement, and the dissemination of scientific findings. It includes outreach programs, public relations, and making data accessible to the global scientific community for further research and collaboration.

ARGOS-CDS

The ARGOS conceptual design study (ARGOS-CDS) mission is **to prepare fully** for the subsequent rapid implementation of the full ARGOS – which aspires to be a leading-edge astronomical instrument in Europe – and ensure its optimal integration into the network of existing and future international astronomical facilities. ARGOS-CDS comprises a 3-year project organized in 9 Work Packages (WPs) to address all relevant scientific, technological, sustainability and policy-making challenges, following a top-down SE approach. ARGOS-CDS objectives are:

- identify and optimize specific science use cases (SUCs) for ARGOS and quantify the corresponding system-wide design requirements to meet these objectives
- produce a comprehensive technical design for ARGOS
- characterize the suitability and sustainability of candidate deployment sites
- assemble an ARGOS prototype for verification, validation and technology pathfinding
- enhance the T&I potential for the EU southern periphery and create capacity for lasting scientific and socioeconomic impact beyond the immediate field of astronomy

These objectives are described in details in [2].

The ARGOS-CDS WBS is described through the project' s WPs which are namely:

- WP1: Management of the project and the consortium
- WP2: Astrophysics
- WP3: System Design Management
- WP4: Site Characterization and Architectural Blueprints
- WP5: Front-end Subsystem
- WP6: Back-end Subsystem
- WP7: Signal-Processing Subsystem
- WP8: Archiving and Alerts Subsystem
- WP9: Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication

In Figure 3 the organization and grouping of the ARGOS-CDS work packages is presented. The diagram illustrates a structured approach to managing the project, with clear delineation of roles and responsibilities. Central to the organization, the Project Management Team (WP1) oversees the entire project, coordinating efforts between various working groups and ensuring alignment with stakeholder expectations and funding policies. The project is divided into two main working groups: the Science Working Group (WP2) and the Engineering Working Group, which includes WPs 3-8. The WP9 acts as a liaison between the science and the engineering working groups.

Figure 3: Work packages organization and grouping

Inside the engineering working group there are strong interconnections as the involved WPs need to fully, transparently and seamlessly cooperate in order to design and eventually build the ambitious full ARGOS telescope. In Figure 4, a schematic diagram of the engineering working group organization is presented. This diagram shows the components in their respective WP and the partner who is responsible for it.

Each WP is responsible for a set of entities that constitute a specific subsystem: WP4 is responsible for the observatory site selection and design; WP5 is responsible for the RF frontend – everything up to the ADCs (antenna, feeder, filters, amplifiers, etc.); WP6 is responsible for the RF backend – digitization, channelization, initial signal processing, distribution to processing units, preparation for the science pipelines; WP7 is responsible for the real-time science experiments that will be executed in parallel – imaging, FRBs detection, Pulsars detection, and calibration; WP8 is responsible for the archiving and alerting of the WP7 and WP6 results; and finally WP3 is responsible for the coordination and management of all the aforementioned WPs and subsystems, including the telescope control system (TCS) and master clock.

Figure 4: The engineering working group (WPs 3-8)

5. System Engineering Phases and Process

ARGOS will follow a structured **Design-Construction-Operation Cycle** (as shown in Figure 5) to ensure the successful deployment and functionality of the 1200 dishes-interferometer array. In the **design phase**, the technical specifications, requirements, and architectural plans are carefully established, considering the scientific goals and performance needs of the array. With 1,200 dishes planned, this phase focuses on developing scalable solutions and robust interfaces among subsystems. The **construction phase** follows, where materials are procured, individual dishes are fabricated and integrated into the overall system, and extensive testing is conducted to validate their performance. This phase requires particular attention to assembly efficiency and quality assurance, given the project's scale.

To manage complexity and mitigate risks, the ARGOS **deployment and operation phase** is split into **two sub-phases**. The first sub-phase will involve constructing and testing an initial set of 100-200 dishes. This initial deployment will serve as an operational test bed (the ARGOS-CDS pathfinder will act as a proof of concept), allowing the project team to validate the design, refine system integration, and address any unforeseen technical issues. If the first sub-phase proves successful, the second sub-phase will proceed to construct and integrate the remaining dishes. This phased approach ensures that ARGOS can scale up effectively, leveraging lessons learned from the initial phase to enhance performance and reliability as the project expands to its full 1,200-dish capacity.

Figure 5: ARGOS life cycle

Definition of the Systems Engineering Process

According to [4] the systems engineering process is a multidisciplinary approach for designing, integrating, and managing complex systems, such as ARGOS, throughout their life cycles. It involves the application of systems principles and methodologies to ensure that all components work together smoothly to meet user requirements and performance goals. This process encompasses requirements definition, system design, implementation, integration, verification, and validation.

Each (sub)system of the ARGOS project will follow the principles of the aforementioned definition, complying with standard SE process methodologies. This ensures that each subsystem is developed, integrated, and managed in a way that aligns with the overall ARGOS goals and requirements. Figure 6 depicts the connections between the activities comprising the SE process as proposed in [5].

Figure 6: Systems Engineering Process

Applying the SE process to each subsystem involves:

1. Requirements Analysis
2. Functional Analysis & Allocation
3. Design Synthesis
4. Systems Analysis & Control
5. Verification and Validation

Requirements Analysis

The Requirements Analysis step involves defining and documenting specific requirements for each (sub)system. Requirements are categorized into functional requirements, which specify what each (sub)system should do, and non-functional requirements, which outline how each (sub)system should perform (e.g., reliability, usability). The Requirements Analysis establishes a solid foundation for subsequent design and development activities, as any gaps or ambiguities identified early in the process can be addressed, ensuring that the system's design aligns closely with the project's objectives and meets all functional, performance, and technical requirements.

Functional Analysis & Allocation

During the Functional Analysis and Allocation process the high-level system requirements are decomposed into lower-level, detailed functional requirements. This process ensures that each function necessary to meet the ARGOS objectives is identified, analyzed, and allocated to specific system components.

First, all the functions that the system must perform to meet the top-level requirements are identified. This involves breaking down the system's overall objectives into smaller, more manageable functions organized into a hierarchical structure. This functional hierarchy must be visualized using functional

flow block diagrams (FFBDs). Each function must be described in detail, specifying what the function does, the conditions under which it operates, and the expected outcomes, including performance criteria for each function.

In the functional allocation phase, each identified function is assigned to specific system components, such as hardware, software, or human operators. Interfaces between components are defined to ensure seamless integration, specifying how different components will interact and exchange information to perform the overall system functions. FFBDs are used to graphically represent the flow of functions and their interrelationships, helping to visualize the sequence of operations and dependencies between functions.

Verification and validation criteria are developed to ensure each function meets its allocated requirements. This includes specifying tests, inspections, and demonstrations, and creating a traceability matrix to ensure all high-level requirements are traced to specific functions and components. The process is iterative, with feedback loops (as it is visualized in Figure 6) to refine and optimize the functional analysis and allocation, involving regular reviews with stakeholders to ensure alignment with user needs and expectations.

Design Synthesis

During the Design Synthesis, abstract functional requirements and architectural decisions are transformed into concrete design specifications for system components. The primary objective is to develop a system architecture that meets all specified requirements, integrates seamlessly with other system components, and is feasible to construct and maintain.

First, multiple design concepts are generated based on the requirements and functional analysis. These concepts are evaluated against criteria such as feasibility, cost, performance, and risk, and the best concept(s) are selected for further development. The selected conceptual design will then be broken down into detailed specifications for individual components, including mechanical, electrical, software, and human interface elements. Interfaces between components are defined to specify how they will interact and exchange information.

Modeling and simulation will play a significant role in this phase. Detailed models of the system and its components are created using CAD tools and simulation software to visualize the design and predict its behavior [6]. Performance simulations are conducted to identify potential issues and optimize the design before building physical prototypes. Prototyping allows for hands-on testing and validation of the design, with any identified issues addressed through iterative refinement.

Integration planning ensures that the various components and subsystems can be successfully combined into a complete system. Compatibility checks and a defined integration strategy help to ensure that all components work together as intended. Throughout the Design Synthesis process, thorough documentation is maintained, including design drawings, specifications, simulation results, test plans, and test results. This documentation is crucial for ensuring that the design can be correctly implemented, verified, and maintained.

The benefits of Design Synthesis include alignment with requirements, risk reduction through early identification and mitigation of issues, and enhanced communication among engineers, stakeholders, and developers. This phase transforms abstract requirements into practical, detailed designs ready for implementation, ensuring that the final system is feasible, efficient, and meets all specified requirements.

System Analysis and Control

Systems Analysis and Control is a critical phase in the SE process, ensuring that the system meets its performance, cost, and schedule objectives. This phase involves continuous evaluation, monitoring, and adjustment of the system design and development activities. The primary objective is to assess system performance, identify and mitigate risks, manage changes, and ensure all components work together in balance.

System analysis involves the assessment of different system alternatives, trade-offs, and design decisions to ensure that the system meets its requirements efficiently. This step includes evaluating technical, functional, and operational aspects to determine the best solutions for the system's design and performance.

System control focuses on monitoring the development progress and ensuring adherence to the defined requirements and design objectives. This involves configuration management, change control, and technical reviews at various stages of the project. By implementing effective control mechanisms, systems engineers can detect any deviations from the plan early, make necessary adjustments, and ensure that the project remains on track to meet performance, cost, and schedule targets. These activities help maintain system integrity and ensure that the final product functions as intended in real-world operations.

Throughout System Analysis and Control, thorough documentation is maintained, including performance analysis reports, risk management plans, configuration management records, change control logs, and verification and validation results.

Verification and Validation

The final design for the ARGOS system will be decided through the process of design verification and validation. Verification and validation ensure the system meets its requirements and functions as intended. Verification involves checking that system components and subsystems meet specified requirements through inspections, tests, and demonstrations. Validation ensures the entire system fulfills its intended purpose in the operational environment, helping identify and correct issues early in the development process and reducing the risk of costly rework.

Design verification will primarily be accomplished through trade-off studies [7], where all design options will be evaluated against a variety of criteria. Cost is a dominant criterion and must be treated with caution in order to ensure that all aspects of the life cycle are included in the cost study. Criteria of pivotal significance are technology maturity, reliability, and power consumption amongst others. Trade-off studies have to be performed for each of these criteria. The aim of all the studies will be to make choices and decisions based on substantial evidence.

Whenever commercial off the shelf (COTS) equipment is being considered in a design application, it must comply with the requirements placed on the applicable element/subsystem which may imply that COTS equipment has to be modified before it can be used in the project. The results and decisions of trade-offs will be documented as part of the design traceability effort.

ARGOS-CDS

The ARGOS-CDS SE process is structured around the phases and milestones depicted in Figure 7. This structure ensures a step-by-step development process, where each phase builds upon the previous one, with key milestones serving as checkpoints to validate progress and readiness to move forward.

Figure 7: System engineering phases of ARGOS

The concept phase involves identifying stakeholders' needs and defining high-level system requirements. This phase sets the foundation for all subsequent development activities by establishing the ARGOS-CDS purpose, scope, and primary objectives. The concept phase is well documented and relevant information can be retrieved from [2].

A stakeholders' workshop (MS1) was held between the concept phase and the preliminary design phase to align the project's direction and gather critical feedback (for more info, please refer to <https://argos-telescope.eu/argos2023/argos2023.html>). During this workshop, stakeholders discussed various design approaches, ensuring that the preliminary designs would meet both the technical specifications and the operational needs. This collaborative session facilitated open communication and helped to refine project objectives as the project transitions into more detailed planning stages.

The definition and preliminary design phase focused on translating the high-level requirements established during the concept phase into detailed specifications and initial designs. This phase involves exploring multiple design options, assessing their feasibility, and selecting the most suitable design approach to meet the system requirements effectively. Documents related to the definition and preliminary design phase are [6], [8] – [9].

The Preliminary Design Review (MS2: PDR) serves as a critical milestone between the preliminary design phase and the detailed design phase (see also Section 7: Reviews). This review will evaluate the preliminary designs to ensure they meet all system requirements and that they are ready for detailed development. The PDR will assess the feasibility, cost, schedule, and risks associated with the designs before advancing to the more detailed and resource-intensive phase of the development the ARGOS pathfinder.

In the detailed design phase the involved engineering teams will refine the selected preliminary designs into comprehensive and precise technical blueprints. This phase includes finalizing specifications for all system components and interfaces, ensuring compatibility and integration readiness for implementation and testing.

The construction of the Pathfinder (MS3) between the detailed design phase and the prototyping phase will enable the testing and refinement of key technological components and design concepts in

a real-world setting, ensuring that the final system design is both practical and effective before full-scale prototyping begins.

The prototyping and validation phase is crucial for identifying and resolving any issues or discrepancies in the ARGOS Pathfinder functionality, ensuring, before full-scale production, that the final 1200-antennas interferometer will be both effective and reliable.

The Critical Design Review (MS4: CDR) serves as the final milestone (see also Section 7: Reviews). This review will thoroughly assess the completeness and correctness of the final design against all system requirements, ensuring that the project is ready to proceed into manufacturing and deployment.

6. Control

This section will describe the control mechanisms that will be deployed to ensure that the engineering effort stays on track and the project meets its objectives. In the context of systems engineering, such control mechanisms include reviews, audits, requirements traceability, risk and change management among others. These are all critical processes for ensuring the quality, compliance, and effectiveness of the full ARGOS and the ARGOS-CDS project. Below we discuss what each of these control mechanisms entails and how it should be operated by the ARGOS (-CDS) consortium.

Reviews

During the lifecycle of the project the following reviews should be conducted:

- Preliminary Design Review (PDR)
- Critical Design Review (CDR)
- Test Readiness Review (TRR)
- Integration and Test Review (ITR)
- Operational Readiness Review (ORR)
- Acceptance Review (AR)
- Post-Implementation Review (PIR)

Firstly, the **Preliminary Design Review (PDR)** evaluates initial design concepts, requirements allocation, and feasibility. It involves the engineering team, project managers, and stakeholders to assess whether the proposed design meets technical requirements and is ready for detailed design.

Secondly, the **Critical Design Review (CDR)** examines the detailed design to verify compliance with specified requirements. This review ensures that the design is mature, risks are mitigated, and readiness for implementation is achieved. It typically includes the engineering team, subject matter experts, and stakeholders.

The **Test Readiness Review (TRR)** assesses readiness to initiate testing and validation activities. It involves test engineers, the quality assurance team, and project managers to ensure that test plans are complete, resources are prepared, and all necessary prerequisites for testing are fulfilled.

The **Integration and Test Review (ITR)** evaluates integration progress and initial test results. It includes the integration team, test engineers, and project managers to assess integration status, identify issues, and verify test outcomes against expected results.

The **Operational Readiness Review (ORR)** evaluates readiness to transition from development to the operational phase. It involves the operations team, maintenance personnel, and project managers to confirm all operational requirements (training, documentation, facilities) are in place for deployment and use.

The **Acceptance Review (AR)** reviews final deliverables against contractual requirements. It includes customer representatives, project managers, and quality assurance to ensure all deliverables meet agreed-upon specifications and are ready for formal acceptance.

Lastly, the **Post-Implementation Review (PIR)** evaluates project performance post-deployment. It involves the project team, stakeholders, and end-users to assess actual performance against expected outcomes, identify lessons learned, and plan improvements or corrective actions as needed.

ARGOS-CDS

During the ARGOS-CDS project, two major reviews will take place: the PDR and the CDR. These reviews are crucial milestones in the systems engineering process, serving to assess and validate the progress and quality of the project's design phases.

The Preliminary Design Review (PDR) is the first major review and occurs after the initial design phase. The primary objective of the PDR is to evaluate the completeness and soundness of the preliminary design of ARGOS-CDS against the system requirements. This review involves a thorough examination of the system's design, including its architecture, components, interfaces, and compliance with performance, safety, and reliability requirements. The PDR ensures that the design is on the right track, identifying any potential issues or risks early in the process. It serves as a checkpoint to verify that the design meets the necessary requirements and is ready to proceed to the detailed design phase.

The CDR is the second major review and occurs after the detailed design phase. The main objective of the CDR is to assess the detailed design's readiness for production and implementation. During the CDR, the detailed design is scrutinized to ensure it meets all system requirements and specifications. This review includes an in-depth analysis of the final design documents, drawings, and specifications, along with verification that all previous review comments and action items have been addressed. The CDR evaluates the system's overall maturity, including its manufacturability, testability, and supportability. It will confirm that the design is robust, feasible, and ready for the next stages of development, such as production, testing, and deployment.

Both the PDR and CDR are essential for ensuring that the project progresses smoothly from the conceptual design phase through to implementation, meeting all technical and functional requirements while minimizing risks and addressing potential issues early in the development process.

Audits

Audits are formal, structured assessments focused on ensuring compliance with standards and regulations. During the full ARGOS lifecycle, the following audits should take place:

- Quality Audit (QA)
- Configuration Audit (CA)
- Safety Audit
- Compliance Audit
- Performance Audit

ARGOS-CDS

No audits are scheduled yet to be conducted throughout the duration of the ARGOS-CDS project.

Requirements Traceability

Requirements traceability will ensure that all requirements from the science find their way down to the lower levels. All requirements will be linked to higher level requirements and will be traceable from requirement specifications, through design documents, through interface control documents (including operator interface documents) down to acceptance test procedures. It is important to establish the link between requirements, supporting design data and, information within the design files because by providing the original context in which a requirement was selected, any future reconsideration of the requirement can determine if the original constraints are still valid. Requirements traceability will be presented and reviewed at each of the technical reviews described previously.

Baseline establishment

Baseline establishment will describe definitive and agreed-upon specifications, designs, and plans that will serve as reference points throughout the project's lifecycle. This process ensures that all stakeholders have a common understanding of the project goals, design parameters, and implementation strategies. The primary objectives are to solidify project requirements, design decisions, and plans to facilitate consistency, traceability, and accountability.

The *requirements baseline* should capture the scientific goals, performance criteria, and technical specifications. The functional baseline defines the system's architecture and the functionality of its components, encompassing the configuration of the antennas, the data acquisition systems, the signal processing units, and the control systems.

The *design baseline* consists of detailed design specifications that provide a comprehensive description of the system's physical and logical design, including mechanical designs, electrical schematics, software architecture, and integration plans. It serves as the foundation for subsequent development and manufacturing activities, ensuring that all design elements are fully documented and conform to the established requirements and functional specifications.

The *development baseline* includes detailed plans for system development, integration, testing, and validation, outlining the schedule, resource allocation, risk management strategies, and testing protocols necessary to ensure the system meets its performance objectives.

Baseline establishment provides a stable foundation for the project's development and management. It ensures that all stakeholders have a shared understanding of the project's objectives, design, and plans, facilitating coordination and reducing the risk of misunderstandings, by providing a clear reference point for tracking progress and managing changes.

Version Control

Version control ensures that all modifications are tracked, documented, and approved in a controlled manner, maintaining the integrity and consistency of the project's subsystems and deliverables.

Version control begins with the establishment of the repository where all project-related files are stored. Each file in this repository is assigned a unique version number that changes whenever a modification is made. Thus, team members can track the history of changes, understand the evolution of the project, and identify which versions of files were used at specific points in the project timeline.

When changes are made to a document, design, or piece of software, the updated version is checked back into the repository with a new version number and a description of the changes made. This practice not only ensures that the most recent versions of all files are readily available to team members but also allows for the retrieval of previous versions if needed. This is crucial for identifying the origins of errors, understanding past decisions, and potentially reverting to earlier versions if new changes introduce issues.

Designated permissions and roles are granted only to authorized personnel who can make changes to certain files. This aspect of control management is critical in a large project like ARGOS where many team members are involved, as it helps prevent unauthorized or unintended modifications that could disrupt the project.

Moreover, version control supports parallel development by allowing multiple team members to work on different parts of the project simultaneously.

Risk Management

Effective risk management is crucial for addressing technical, financial, and operational uncertainties. The first step in risk management is identifying potential risks. This involves a thorough analysis of the entire project, including technical aspects, design processes, budget considerations, schedule constraints, and operational requirements. Risks arise from various sources, such as technology limitations, integration challenges, supplier reliability, environmental factors, and regulatory compliance.

Once risks are to be identified, their likelihood and potential impact shall be assessed through a qualitative and quantitative analysis. Risks will be rated as low, medium, or high, helping prioritize which ones require immediate attention.

After assessing risks, mitigation strategies will be developed and implemented. Mitigation will involve alternative technologies, redesigning components, increasing redundancy, conducting additional testing, or securing backup suppliers. Each mitigation plan includes specific actions, assigned responsibilities, and timelines. The mitigation plans must be taken into account into the overall project schedule and budget to ensure they are feasible and effective.

Relevant information on Risk management in ARGOS can also be found in Risk Management subsection of the present document and in [2].

Logistics

Logistics assessment shall ensure that all necessary resources, materials, and services are efficiently procured, transported, and managed. Key considerations include the size and weight of components, special handling requirements, transportation routes, and storage facilities.

Effective supply chain management is crucial, involving the identification and selection of reliable suppliers, negotiation of contracts, and establishment of delivery schedules. Transportation planning

shall consider factors like cost, time, and the nature of the items. Special handling techniques are employed for oversized or delicate parts to prevent damage during transit.

Site preparation ensures that the installation site has the necessary infrastructure, such as access roads, cranes, and storage facilities, to support delivery and assembly operations. Proper inventory management tracks the receipt, storage, and usage of components, preventing delays caused by missing or misplaced parts and ensuring materials are protected while in storage.

Logistics for assembly and integration involve coordinating the arrival of components with the project schedule to ensure timely availability for assembly. This requires detailed planning to sequence deliveries and avoid bottlenecks, with close coordination between logistics and assembly teams.

Comprehensive documentation and reporting track the progress of logistical activities and ensure accountability, providing insights into the status of operations and helping project managers make informed decisions.

Quality

Quality control begins with the establishment of comprehensive quality standards and specifications that align with the project's scientific goals and technical requirements.

During the design phase, quality is controlled by conducting thorough design reviews and analyses. These reviews involve cross-disciplinary teams of experts who scrutinize the design for potential flaws, ensure compliance with specifications, and verify that all functional requirements are addressed. Tools such as failure mode and effects analysis (FMEA) and fault tree analysis (FTA) will be used to identify potential failure points and mitigate risks early in the design process.

In the manufacturing phase, quality control involves strict adherence to established procedures and standards. This includes selecting high-quality materials, using precision manufacturing techniques, and implementing robust assembly processes. Any deviations from the standards are documented and corrected promptly to prevent defective components from progressing through the assembly process.

Testing and validation are critical stages in quality control. Components and subsystems undergo rigorous testing under simulated operational conditions to verify their performance and reliability. These tests include environmental stress testing, where components are exposed to extreme temperatures, vibrations, and other conditions they might encounter in actual use. The system will be tested for its mechanical performance, ensuring that it meets the precise alignment and sensitivity requirements necessary for accurate scientific observations.

Continuous improvement is a key aspect of quality control. Feedback from testing and operational use is used to refine and enhance the design and manufacturing processes.

7. Retirement

The retirement plan should ensure that the project's assets are preserved, the data remains accessible, and any ongoing obligations are fulfilled. Several steps are involved in such a process, an outline of which follows:

Documentation and Knowledge Transfer:

- **Complete Documentation:** Ensure that all project documentation is up to date, including design documents, user manuals, maintenance logs, and software documentation.
- **Knowledge Transfer Sessions:** Conduct sessions to transfer knowledge to relevant stakeholders, such as researchers, maintenance teams, or successor projects.

Data Preservation:

- **Data Backup:** Create backups of data collected by the project. Store these backups in different physical and cloud locations.
- **Data Archiving:** Use standardized and accessible formats for long-term data storage. Ensure that metadata is comprehensive for future use.
- **Public Repositories:** Deposit data in public repositories where it can be accessed by the scientific community.

Hardware and Infrastructure:

- **Decommissioning Plan:** Develop a detailed plan for the safe decommissioning of hardware, including antennas, mounts, receivers, and other RF components.
- **Reuse or Disposal:** Evaluate whether any components can be reused in other projects or need to be disposed of safely and in compliance with regulations.
- **Facility Repurposing:** If applicable, repurpose the physical facilities for other scientific or educational uses.

Software Management:

- **Open-source Release:** Consider releasing the project's software as open source, ensuring that it includes all necessary documentation for future developers.
- **Repository Maintenance:** Host the software on a public repository (e.g., GitHub, GitLab) and provide clear instructions for use and further development.
- **Legacy Support:** Identify a period for which legacy support (bug fixes, minor updates) will be provided and designate a team or individual responsible for this.

Financial and Administrative Tasks:

- **Final Budget Review:** Conduct a final review of the project budget to ensure all financial obligations are met.
- **Reporting:** Prepare and submit final project reports to all stakeholders, including funding agencies, collaborators, and institutional bodies.
- **Legal and Compliance:** Ensure all legal and compliance issues are addressed, including data protection regulations and intellectual property rights.

Stakeholder Communication:

- **Notification:** Inform all stakeholders of the project's retirement plan and timeline, including collaborators, funding bodies, and the scientific community.
- **Final Publication:** Publish a final report or paper summarizing the project's achievements, findings, and contributions to the field.

Post-Retirement Review:

- **Lessons Learned:** Conduct a thorough review of the project to document lessons learned and best practices for future projects.
- **Legacy Planning:** Ensure there is a plan in place to address any long-term impacts or requirements that may arise after the project has been retired.

Example Timeline for Retirement Plan Execution:

- **Months 1-3:**
 - Update and complete documentation.
 - Conduct knowledge transfer sessions.
 - Begin data backup and archiving processes.
- **Months 4-6:**
 - Develop and start implementing the decommissioning plan for hardware.
 - Prepare software for open-source release and set up repository.
- **Months 7-9:**
 - Conduct final budget review and prepare final reports.
 - Notify all stakeholders and prepare final publication.
- **Months 10-12:**
 - Complete decommissioning of hardware and repurposing of facilities.
 - Finalize data archiving and ensure long-term access.
 - Conduct post-retirement review and document lessons learned.

By following this structured approach, we can ensure a smooth and responsible retirement of the ARGOS project, preserving its legacy and providing valuable resources for future research and development.

8. Documentation and Additional Activities

Reports

The reporting requirements for the project are described in detail in [2]. The periodic report to the commission should contain a summary, project objectives for the period, work progress and achievements, updates on deliverable and milestones, report on PMT activities, explanation on use of resources, financial statements from each partner and audit certificates. A template with the typical report structure is provided in Appendix A at the end of this document.

Deliverables

The ARGOS-CDS deliverables are established by the Grant Agreement [1].

Repository

ARGOS-CDS maintains a NextCloud repository that is accessible to all team members [2]. This repository serves as a central hub where team members can find essential materials, and it also provides a platform for uploading reports and deliverables.

Communication Channels

The project team members have access to the following communication channels [2]:

- **Face-to-Face (F2F):** For direct, in-person meetings and discussions.
- **Phone:** For voice communications and urgent discussions.
- **Text Messaging:** For quick and informal communications.
- **Email:** For formal communications, document sharing, and official announcements.
- **Mattermost:** For team collaboration and real-time messaging.
- **Slack:** For instant messaging and team collaboration.
- **Skype:** For video conferencing and online meetings.
- **Zoom:** For virtual meetings and webinars.
- **Social Media:** For public updates and community engagement.

Safety

Safety measures are essential components of the SEMP in order to ensure that the system being developed is safe during its development and for its intended use. Key safety measures that are considered in ARGOS-CDS are:

- Specific international safety standards and regulations should govern the design, development, and operation of the system. Such standards are IEC 61511 [10], IEC 62061 [11] NEMA-MG 2-2014 [12] among others.
- All involved parties should comply with the aforementioned safety standards and regulations. Industry best practices should be applicable to the system and its intended use. This includes incorporating the latest advancements in safety technology, following rigorous testing protocols, and ensuring continuous improvement in safety measures.

9. Appendix A: Templates

Deliverable Template

This template includes placeholders and standardized sections to streamline the creation of the ARGOS (and ARGOS-CDS) deliverables

The template includes:

- **Cover Page:** Placeholder for title, version, release date, author, and dissemination level.
- **Document History:** Table for version, date, content and changes, and edited by.
- **Peer Reviewed By:** Table for partner, reviewer, and version reviewed.
- **Approved By:** Table for partner, name, and signature.
- **Disclaimer:** Placeholder for disclaimer text.
- **Table of Contents:** Placeholder for autogenerated table of contents.
- **Main Sections:** Placeholders for each main section of the document (e.g., Introduction, References, etc.)
- **Appendix:** Placeholder for appendices and templates

Report Template

This template includes placeholders and standardized sections to streamline the creation of the ARGOS (and ARGOS-CDS) reports

The template includes:

- **Introduction**
- **(Sub)System description**
- **(Sub)System requirements**
- **Overall architecture**
- **Software, hardware components and interfaces**
- **Results & actualization**
- **Conclusions**

PDR Response Template

This template includes placeholders and standardized sections to streamline the creation of the ARGOS (and ARGOS-CDS) PDR response

The template includes:

- **Overall System Design Feedback**
- **Requirements traceability**
- **Risk Assessment and management**
- **Subsystems and Interfaces**
- **Test and Verification Plans**
- **Schedule and Budget Considerations**
- **Standards and Compliance**
- **Review Board Decisions**

ARGOS

Conceptual Design Study

Designing a Next-Generation Radio Facility for Multi-Messenger Astronomy

Deliverable No: **D#.#**
Deliverable/Document Name: **name**
Version: **0.1**
Release date: **Dd/mm/yyyy**
Dissemination level: **Public**
Status: **[Submitted/Accepted]**
Author: **FirstName LastName**

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Document history

Version	Date	Content and changes	Edited by
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Peer reviewed by

Partner	Reviewer	Version Reviewed
Partner's Name	FirstName LastName	

Approved by

Partner	Name	Signature

Disclaimer

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¹ Drafts should be version numbered "0.1", "1.2", etc. Accepted Releases should be version numbered "1.0", "2.0", etc

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Scope of the document

Fill appropriate text

Content of the document

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2. References

Applicable documents

In the event of conflict between the contents of the following documents and this document, the following documents shall take precedence.

[1] Refer. 1

[2] Refer. 2

Reference documents

In the event of conflict between the contents of the following documents and this document, this document shall take precedence.

[3] Refer. 3

[4] Refer. 4

[5] Refer. 5

.....

3. Section

Subsection

Fill appropriate text

Subsection

Fill appropriate text. Refer to Figure 1

Figure 1: example high-level overview of ARGOS

4. Section

Subsection

Subsubsection

5. Appendix A: Templates

ARGOS

Conceptual Design Study

Designing a Next-Generation Radio Facility for Multi-Messenger Astronomy

Report Name: **name**
Release date: **Dd/mm/yyyy**
Author: **FirstName LastName**

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Document history

Version	Date	Content and changes	Edited by
1	Dd/mm/yyyy	FirstName LastName	FirstName LastName

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List of Abbreviations

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Content of the document

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[1] Refer. 1

[2] Refer. 2

Reference documents

In the event of conflict between the contents of the following documents and this document, this document shall take precedence.

[3] Refer. 3

[4] Refer. 4

[5] Refer. 5

.....

3. (Sub)System description

Mission of the subsystem

Science governing the subsystem

Maintenance and support of the subsystem

Relevant existing technologies

4. (Sub)System requirements

Mapping to lower-level requirements

5. Overall architecture

High level structure and interconnectivity diagrams

[Refer to](#) Figure 1

Figure 1: example high-level overview of ARGOS

Description of operation (i.e. use cases)
Subsystems and interoperability – functional and physical architecture breakdowns
Dataflow diagrams
Sequence diagrams
[* use Capella produced diagrams where applicable for uniformity]

6. Software, hardware components and interfaces

Software: subsystems, specific components, interfaces
Hardware: subsystems, specific components, interfaces
Network or other type of communication interface: subsystems, specific components, interfaces

7. Results & actualization

Results on tests performed on verification models
Scaling analysis
Deployment Plan
Upgrade Plan

8. Conclusions

Open issues

9. Appendix A: Templates

ARGOS

Conceptual Design Study

Designing a Next-Generation Radio Facility for Multi-Messenger Astronomy

Project Title: **ARGOS-CDS**
Document Name: **Preliminary Design Review Template**
Review Board Members: **1st Reviewer's Name**
2nd Reviewer's Name
3rd Reviewer's Name
Review Date:
Dissemination level: **Public**
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1. Overall System Design Feedback

Related Documents to Review

- SEMP (ICS)
- Site Characterization and Architectural Blueprints report (ICS)

Summary of Design Feasibility

[Comment on the overall feasibility of the system design. Is the design sound, and are the chosen technologies appropriate for the project's goals?]

Strengths

[Highlight the strong points of the design, such as novel approaches, robustness, scalability, or efficiency.]

Weaknesses, Concerns or Gaps

[List concerns regarding the system design. This might include incomplete design elements, untested technology, or gaps in addressing key requirements.]

Recommendations

[Provide suggestions on how to address the concerns, such as performing additional trade studies, changing a design approach, or enhancing system-level modeling.]

2. Requirements Traceability

Related Documents to Review

- L0 requirements (IA)
- L1 specifications (ICS)

Summary

[Is the design traceable to the system requirements? Have all key performance parameters been addressed?]

Missing or Incomplete Requirements

[Identify any requirements that have not been adequately addressed in the design.]

Recommendations

[Recommend ways to ensure all requirements are fully addressed in the design. This may include further refinement of specifications, updating interface control documents, or conducting additional validation.]

3. Risk Assessment and management

Related Documents to Review

- Risk register (ICS)

Summary of Risks

[Comment on the quality of the risk management plan and the adequacy of risk mitigation strategies.]

Major Risks Identified

[Highlight significant risks associated with the preliminary design (technical, schedule, budgetary risks, etc.)]

Risk Mitigation Recommendations

[Provide recommendations for improving the mitigation strategies for key risks. Suggest further analysis or testing for high-risk areas.]

4. Subsystems and Interfaces

Related Documents to Review

- Front-end Subsystem design (UPRC)
- Back-end Subsystem design (MPIfR)
- Signal-Processing Subsystem design (CEA)
- Archiving and Alerts Subsystem design (ICS)
- IDC TCS (IA)
- IDC Backend (MPIfR)
- IDC Feed -> RF Board (UPRC)

Subsystem Design

[Evaluate the subsystem designs based on the documents. Are the designs sufficiently detailed? Are key performance metrics addressed?]

Interface Issues

[Identify any issues or unclear specifications between subsystem interfaces as outlined in the IDCs.]

Recommendations

[Provide suggestions for improving subsystem designs and interfaces. Refer to the specific ICD or subsystem document that requires updates.]

5. Test and Verification Plans

Related Documents to Review

- Verification Plan (IA)

Summary of Test Plans

[Assess whether the test and verification plans are sufficient to ensure that the system will meet its requirements.]

Missing Test Strategies

[Identify any missing test strategies based on the reviewed test plan, especially for critical subsystems.]

Recommendations

[Recommend additional testing methods or simulations. Refer to the specific test plan or verification matrix that needs to be updated.]

6. Schedule and Budget Considerations

Related Documents to Review

- SEMP (ICS)

Feasibility of Schedule

[Evaluate the feasibility of the project schedule based on the reviewed schedule documents. Are key milestones realistic?]

Budget Evaluation

[Comment on the alignment of the budget with the current design complexity based on the cost estimates and WBS.]

Recommendations

[Provide suggestions for managing schedule or budget risks. Reference specific sections of the schedule or budget documents that need further review.]

7. Standards and Compliance

Related Documents to Review

- SEMP (ICS)
- RISK register (ICS)

Compliance Assessment

[Evaluate whether the design complies with relevant industry standards and regulatory requirements.]

Safety and Reliability

[Review the safety and reliability analysis. Are there any areas of concern related to system reliability?]

Recommendations

[Provide suggestions to address any compliance or reliability concerns based on the reviewed documents.]

8. Review Board Decisions

Go/No-Go Decision

[Summarize the review board's decision on whether the project is ready to proceed to the detailed design phase based on the reviewed documentation.]

Action Items

[Provide a detailed list of action items that need to be addressed before proceeding to the next phase. Each action item should be linked to a specific document or issue identified during the review.]

Additional Comments

[Include any other relevant comments that may not have been captured in the previous sections but are based on the reviewed documents.]